

LEGALITY OF THE WAR AGAINST IRAQ: A PASSING FRENZY?

Aisha S. Maikudi*

I. INTRODUCTION.

The question of the legality of the 2003 war against Iraq is a contentious matter amongst lawyers. It demonstrated the law's ambiguity for both the anti-war and pro-war groups claimed that the law was on their side¹. Seven (7) years after the war, the issues of *jus in bello* (actual conduct of armed conflict) and *jus ad bellum* (legality of the use of force) that took the legal world by storm have now taken a backseat. The worlds legal community is quiet. Has the 2003 war against Iraq become a passing frenzy?

This analysis will solely be on the legality of the use of force in International Law (*jus ad bellum*). It will not discuss the rules governing the actual conduct of armed conflict (*jus in bello*) neither will it discuss the moral issues of war.

A. The use of force in International Law and the content of this report.

It is important to begin by reviewing the use of force and law through the history of mankind. The first of which is the 'just and unjust war' doctrine. The 'just war' doctrine was predicated by Christianity². War is just if undertaken as a means of restating the status quo. In the Thirteenth Century St Thomas Aquinas, wrote that for war to be 'just' it had to fulfil three conditions:

- i) the war had to be conducted not privately but under the authority of a Prince;
- ii) there had to be a 'just cause' for the war; and
- iii) it was not enough to have a just cause from an objective point of view, but it was necessary to have the right intention to promote good and to avoid evil³.

* LL.B (HONS.), LLM (lonD), B.L, Lecturer, Faculty of Law, University of Abuja, Gwagwalada, FCT, Nigeria. E-mail: ayeesha31@yahoo.co.uk

¹ J. Ralph, *International Journal of Human Rights*, Vol. 8, No.2, pg 236, summer 2004.

² One of the first major Christian figures to write on the subject was St Augustine (AD 354-430).

³ This third doctrine is of divine roots; that is good and evil.

The just war doctrine was divorced from its ideological and divine roots and redefined in terms of vital interests (that is, self-defence, the protection of property and the punishment for wrongs suffered) by Hugo Grotius in his *De Jure Belli ac Pacis*.⁴ This 'just war' doctrine is a paradox. In almost all conflicts, justice is wanted by both parties which they believe in.

So the first salient question thrown up in understanding the objectively defined legality of war is: can two, mutually exclusive, conflicting notions of peace and justice held by two opposing parties contemplating war both be deemed valid? The inescapable conclusion here is that, contrary to the clear exhortation of St Thomas of Aquinas that justice in any given situation be defined "objectively", in implementation, justice is often highly subjective. Indeed, given that war has been a constant factor in recorded human history, the unavoidable conclusion is that notions of justice clearly vary according to perspective.

In the 19th and 20th Century, the system was focused more on the peaceful methods of settling disputes. The first legal limitations on the use of force came from The Hague Peace Conferences (1899-1907), the League of Nations Covenant and the Kellogg Briand Pact of 1928.

Through the covenant of the League of Nations signed in 1919, States sought to establish a comprehensive regulation of the use of force. Its aims were to promote international co-operation and to achieve international peace and security. The covenant did not abolish the right of States to resort to war it only restricted that right in accordance with Article 12(1) of the Covenant which holds that States are required initially to submit their disputes to settlement and if that did not work they effectively recovered their right to resort to force. However, States got round the covenant by saying; although a lot of force is being used it does not amount to the prohibited use of force. War through self-defence or as an instrument of international policy; that is, sanctioned by the United Nations, still remained lawful.

The League, the 'great experiment that failed', may nevertheless claim its place in history as the precursor to the United Nations: much of the United Nations system drew on experience

⁴ Hugo Grotius, THE LAW OF WAR AND PEACE (1625), Extracts in Selections of Grotius' DE JURE BELLI AC PACIS, trans. W.S.M. Knight (Grotius Society Publications, 1922), vol. 3.

gained from the attempts to develop the League system.⁵ Potter holds the view that the League ‘made a far greater contribution to the progress of international organisation than any other institution in our history’.

Article I of the Kellogg-Briand Pact condemns and provided for outlawing war between States as an ‘an instrument of national policy in their relations with one another’ whilst Article II refers to the settlement of disputes only by ‘peaceful means’. The Treaty contained no enforcement mechanism for changing the behaviour of warring signatories and was interpreted by most of the signatories to permit ‘defensive’ war. No expiration date was provided and no provision existed for amending the agreement was included. Despite these shortcomings, the Pact was signed in August 1928 by 15 Nations. In the following months, more than 60 countries joined in this renunciation of war. The United Nations which is the largest International Organization was then created in 1945. This analysis will concentrate on this institution.

B. General prohibition established by the United Nations Charter.

The United Nations Charter was drafted against the background of the fear of a Third World War at a time when the whole of Europe was economically and physically in ruins from the Second World War. The Charter's preamble states that ‘we the peoples of the United Nations (are) determined to save succeeding generations from the scourge of war, which twice in our lifetime has brought untold sorrow to mankind’. To this end, Article 1 of the Charter holds that the purpose of the United Nations is ‘to maintain international peace and security’.

Article 2(3) of the United Nations Charter states:

All Members shall refrain their international disputes by peaceful means in such a manner that international peace and security, and justice, are not endangered.

Article 2(4) is a general ban on the use of force by states. It is a norm of Customary International Law and is of universal validity. It ‘introduces into International Law the most far-reaching limitation ever adopted on the use of force by States against one another’⁶:

⁵ D. Bowett, ‘SELF DEFENCE IN INTERNATIONAL LAW’. (Manchester: Manchester University Press 1958).

All members shall refrain in their international relations from the threat or use of force against the territorial integrity or political independence of any State, or in any other manner inconsistent with the purposes of the United Nations⁷.

Article 2(3) refers to a positive duty whilst Article 2(4) is a negative duty thus, they complement each other. What is meant by 'force' in Article 2(4)? Since the 1990's, there has been disagreement over the meaning of the use of force. Nevertheless, it is construed broadly. Direct force is prohibited and so is indirect force as confirmed by the International Court of Justice in the *Nicaragua*⁸ case which determined that the arming and training of insurgents was a use of force⁹.

C. The two exceptions: Self-defence and Security Council authorisation.

There are two exceptions to the fundamental prohibition on the use of force in the United Nations Charter. These exceptions must be read restrictively. The first is the right of self-defence. The essence of this is self-help. A State may respond by self-defence to an attack. It is a right both in the Charter and in customary international law¹⁰. Necessity and proportionality are at the heart of self-defence.

Traditionally, the *Caroline*¹¹ case set out the status of self-defence. This case involved the British seizing an American ship from an American port because its crew had been assisting - with some success- in the Canadian rebellion of that time. The British attacked the rebels and crew on board, then 'fired' the ship and sent it over the edge of Niagara Falls. This resulted in the death of two Americans which led to a series of correspondence between the British and American governments in which the British claimed that their act was one of self-defence due to the actions of the rebels and crew on board, and the possibility of further actions.

⁶ Christopher Greenwood, *International Law and Pre-emptive Use of Force: Afghanistan, Al-Qaida, and Iraq*, 4 San Diego Jnl Int 7.

⁷ UNITED NATIONS CHARTER ARTICLE 2(4).

⁸ *Nicaragua v. United States of America* I.C.J Reports 1986

⁹ The Court did not consider the provision of funding to be a use of force.

¹⁰ *Nicaragua case*, supra note 8, at para.174.

¹¹ *Caroline case* (1837). 2 Moore's digest, Vol.II at pg. 409.

American response from Daniel Webster (then Secretary of State) was that for a claim of self-defence to be legitimate the British must demonstrate that there existed a ‘necessity of self-defence, instant and overwhelming, and leaving no choice of means, and no moment for deliberation... (the action must also not be) unreasonable or excessive’.¹² These principles were accepted by the British government at the time and became accepted as part of Customary International Law.

The right of self defence has been codified in the United Nations Charter. Article 51 of the Charter holds that: ‘Nothing in the present Charter shall impair the inherent right of individual or collective self-defence...’ Some commentators hold that Article 2(4) limits the scope of the right to only if a country has been attacked whilst others give more weight to the opening of Article 51.

The second exception recognised by the United Nations Charter is the use of force via Security Council authorisation. The Security Council’s primary responsibility is ‘the maintenance of international peace and security’¹³. Chapter VII details the extensive powers available to the Security Council and establishes the legal framework by which the Security Council can employ those considerable powers. The extent of the power granted to the Security Council is considerable. Prof Dinstein goes as far as to suggest that ‘the degree of latitude bestowed upon it by the charter is well-nigh unlimited’¹⁴.

The trigger to the measures available to the Security Council is Article 39 of the Charter which provides for a determination of ‘the existence of any threat to the peace, breach of peace or act of aggression’ by the Security Council. Provisional measures are given under Article 40 of the Charter whilst Article 41 provides for non-military enforcement measures such as, economic sanctions. Forceful measures are authorised via Article 42 of the United Nations Charter.

II. THE SECURITY COUNCIL RESOLUTIONS ON IRAQ.

¹² Letter from Daniel Webster to Henry S. Fox (Apr 24, 1842), quoted in LORI DAMROSCH, INTERNATIONAL LAW: CASES AND MATERIALS 923 (2001).

¹³ UNITED NATIONS CHARTER, ARTICLE 24(1).

¹⁴ Y.Dinstein, WAR, AGGRESSION AND SELF-DEFENCE, 3rd ed., (2001).

Chapter VII of the Charter gives the Security Council the authority to determine the existence of a threat to the peace, breach of the peace or act of aggression and to authorise actions accordingly.

The first Security Council Resolution on Iraq is Resolution 660¹⁵ which was passed on 2 August 1990. Acting under Articles 39 and 40 of the United Nations Charter, the Security Council determined that there existed a breach of International peace and security. The invasion of Kuwait by Iraq was condemned, Iraq was ordered to ‘withdraw immediately’ and both Countries were called upon to solve their differences. Resolution 660 laid the foundation for all subsequent United Nations action against Iraq. This paper will concentrate on the three main Resolutions on Iraq which are Resolutions 678(1990), 687(1991) and 1441(2002).

A. Resolution 678 (1990): Original authorisation to use force in Iraq.

This Resolution contains only five short paragraphs. Adopted via Chapter VII of the United Nations Charter, Resolution 678¹⁶ was passed on 29 November 1990 by twelve votes to two (Cuba and Yemen) and one abstention (China).

Resolution 678 gave Iraq until January 15, 1991, to withdraw from Kuwait and if that deadline was not met, authorised the use of all necessary means for the specific purpose of upholding earlier Resolutions. Resolution 678 paragraph 2, gave the authorisation to use force. It holds:

Member States co-operating with the Government of Kuwait, unless Iraq on or before 15 January 1991 fully implements, as set forth in paragraph 1 above, the foregoing resolutions, to use all necessary means to uphold and implement Security Council Resolution 660 (1990) and all subsequent relevant resolutions and to restore international peace and security in the area.

Resolution 678 thus provided an enforcement mechanism for Resolution 660 adopted the day Iraq invaded Kuwait, (which made the determination required by the United Nations Charter as a precondition for the collective use of force, that the invasion constituted a breach of

¹⁵ S.C. Res. 660, (Aug, 2, 1990), U.N.Doc. S/RES/660 (1990).

¹⁶ S.C. Res. 678, (Nov, 29, 1990), 29 ILM 1565 (1990).

international peace and security) and the subsequent reiterations of that Resolution between August and November 1990¹⁷.

This Resolution is very ambiguous. Greenwood suggests that this ambiguity is deliberate because the Security Council was trying to make the Resolution ‘more palatable to China, which might have vetoed anything too obviously reminiscent of Korea’¹⁸. The ambiguity of Resolution 678 has caused problems with the question of what the legal basis of the war against Iraq was in 1990. Was it ‘an instance of enforcement action by the Security Council or merely a case of the Council giving its blessing to an action based upon the right of self-defence’¹⁹? The degree of control given to the coalition has strengthened some commentators’ case who argue that it was a collective self-defence action based on Article 51 of the Charter²⁰.

However, this seems highly unlikely because an action in self-defence needs neither Security Council authorisation nor its blessings. Furthermore, an action of self-defence does not extend to securing peace and security in the area which Resolution 678 expressly states²¹. This poses the question, how wide is the scope for restoring peace and security? Does it extend to the situation in Iraq as of March 18, 2003?

To sum it all up, Resolution 676 gives Member States co-operating with the Government of Kuwait the authority to ‘use all necessary means’ to make sure Iraq leaves Kuwait, Iraq complies with all previous Resolutions and to restore peace and security in the area.

B. Resolution 687 (1991): Ceasefire obligations.

Security Council Resolution 687²² was enacted through Chapter VII of the United Nations Charter on 3 April 1991 by twelve votes to one (Cuba) with two abstentions (Ecuador and Yemen). This Resolution sets out the ceasefire obligations. Like all the earlier Resolutions on

¹⁷ Hilary Charlesworth & Andrew Byrnes, ‘No this war is illegal’. <http://www.theage.com.au/articles>.

¹⁸ Christopher Greenwood, ‘*New World Order or Old? The Invasion of Kuwait and the Rule of Law*’, *Modern Law Review* 55:2 March 1992, pg.153.

¹⁹ Greenwood, *ibid*, at p. 167

²⁰ See for example: Rostow, ‘Until What? Enforcement action or Collective Self-Defence?’, 85 *AJIL* (1991) pg.506.

²¹ SC Res. 678, *supra* note 16, at para 2.

²² S.C.Res 687, (Apr. 3, 1991), 30 *ILM* 846 (1991).

Iraq, Resolution 687 affirms all the previous Resolutions on Iraq²³. Resolution 687 is usually referred to as the ‘mother of all Resolutions’.

In its preamble, Resolution 687 reiterates Iraq’s recognition of the independence and complete sovereignty of the State of Kuwait with its boundaries as specified in the letter of the Prime Minister of Iraq dated 21 July 1932 and accepted by the ruler of Kuwait in his letter dated 10 August 1932.

Subject to Iraq’s compliance with Security Council Resolution 686, paragraph 6 of Resolution 687 terminated the authorization of the use force to drive out Iraq from Kuwait. It: Notes that as soon as the Secretary-General notifies the Security Council of the completion of the deployment of the United Nations observer unit, the conditions will be established for the Member States cooperating with Kuwait in accordance with resolution 678 (1990) to bring their military presence in Iraq to an end consistent with resolution 686(1991);

Resolution 687 also introduced multiple disarmament demands on Iraq. Paragraph 8 states that Iraq:

unconditionally accept the destruction, removal, or rendering harmless, under international supervision of:

- a) All chemical and biological weapons and all stocks of agents and all related subsystems and components and all research, development, support and manufacturing facilities related hereto;
- b) All ballistic missiles with a range greater than one hundred and fifty kilometres, and related major parts and repair and productions facilities.’

Under paragraph 12, Iraq was required:

Not to acquire or develop nuclear weapons or nuclear-weapon-usable material or any subsystems or components or any research, development, support or manufacturing facilities related to the above.

Resolution 687 paragraph 16 ‘reaffirmed that Iraq is liable for all its debts and obligations...’ The word ‘reaffirmed’ is a bit problematic because this is a legal matter and not a Security Council matter. Nevertheless, there is no doubt that in the law of State responsibility, Iraq is liable. Paragraph 18 then states the aim of establishing the United Nations compensation committee. This was set up by Resolution 692²⁴. Initially, there was a levy of 30% which was reduced to 25% and finally to 5% on Iraqi oil. There were 26 million claims around the

²³ Thirteen Resolutions in this case.

²⁴ SC Res. 692 (May, 20, 1991), U.N. Docs. S/RES/692 (1990).

region of \$300 billion with some 100 State Nationals being involved. The Compensation Committee got about \$50 billion and was able to pay out \$19 billion²⁵.

Iraq was further required not to ‘commit or support any act of international terrorism or for any such organisation to operate within its territory’²⁶. This Resolution also declared that the economic sanctions on Iraq will remain until inspectors certify it is free of weapons of mass destruction. Thus, the debate since 1991 has been about whether sanctions should be lifted or not and not about Member States using military force to rid Iraq of weapons of mass destruction and the means to produce them²⁷.

Although this Resolution was passed under Chapter VII of the United Nations Charter and as such is binding on Iraq, paragraph 33 states that the ceasefire obligations that are set out in the Resolution are made effective ‘upon official notification by Iraq to the Secretary-General and to the Security Council of its acceptance’.

The Resolution leaves open the issue of what will happen if Iraq does not comply with its terms, implying that the Security Council will need to consider the matter when further evidence appears.

In a nutshell, Resolution 687 requires Iraq to renounce its territorial claim to Kuwait, to sever any links with terrorism and provides for certain specified stages of disarmament.

C. Resolution 1441 (2002): Aimed at the eradication of weapons of mass destruction.

Acting under Chapter VII of the United Nations Charter, Resolution 1441²⁸ was unanimously adopted by the Security Council on 8 November 2002. Although, in standard Security Council style, all previous Resolutions on Iraq are referred to in the preamble of Resolution 1441, there is no paragraph that suggests United Nations Member States may take ‘all necessary means’ to implement the Resolution. Indeed, France, China and Russia (3 of the 5 veto wielding States) made a public interpretative statement on Resolution 1441 on the day it

²⁵ www.unorg.ch/uncc.

²⁶ SC Res. 687, para 32 (Apr. 3, 1991), 30 ILM 846 (1991).

²⁷ See for example, the debate on Operation Desert Fox. U.N. SCOR 53d Sess., 3955th mtg., U.N. Doc. S/PV. 3955, Dec 16, 1998.

²⁸ SC. Res. 1441, (Nov. 8, 2002), 42 ILM 250 (2003).

was adopted, noting they voted for the Resolution precisely because it contained no ‘automaticity’ in the use of force²⁹. This understanding was confirmed in the United States and United Kingdom's formal explanation of their votes.

Paragraph 1 of the Resolution finds Iraq to be in ‘material breach’ of the previous Security Council Resolutions and in particular, of Resolutions 678 and 687. The Council then decides to give Iraq ‘a finally opportunity to comply with its disarmament obligations’³⁰.

Paragraph 4 holds that ‘false statements or omissions...shall constitute a further material breach of Iraq’s obligations...’ There is a peculiar argument about this concept of a ‘material breach’. The argument put forward is keyed to Article 60 of the Vienna Convention on the law of Treaties which holds that a party affected by a material breach of a multilateral Treaty may invoke it as a ground of suspending the operation of the Treaty in part or in whole in relations with the defaulting State. In the case of a material breach, the parties may respond where appropriate by coercive measures³¹.

Under the United Nations Charter, Member States are made to comply with Security Council Resolutions adopted under Chapter VII. Thus, such Resolutions are similar to multilateral Treaties (although not exactly) in that they are binding instruments under International Law. When the Security Council held in paragraph 1 of Resolution 1441 that Iraq is in material breach of its obligations under relevant Resolutions, including Resolution 687, it appears to have treated those Resolutions as being sufficiently like multilateral Treaties to be subject to Article 60 of the Vienna Convention³².

Another angle to this would be, since the United Nations Charter says that Security Council decisions embodied in Chapter VII Resolutions are binding on all members, a material breach of such a Resolution by a United Nations Member State (such as Iraq) would be a material breach of the Charter itself. Since the Charter is a multilateral treaty, Article 60 of the Vienna Convention would apply directly to any material breach of it.

²⁹ S.PV.4644 (8 November 2002).

³⁰ SC. Res 1441, *supra* note 28, at para 2.

³¹ Frederic L. Kirgis, ‘*Security Council Resolution 1441 on Iraq’s Final Opportunity to Comply with Disarmament Obligations*’, ASIL Insights. http://www.asil.org/insights/insigh92.htm#_edn2

³² Kirgis, *ibid* note 31

However, this argument is weak. This is because Treaties are reached through negotiations unlike Security Council Resolutions which must be respected by all parties with or without their consent³³. They are enforced by the Security Council and not by individual States. Furthermore, under the United Nations Charter, States may only use force in cases of self-defence or Security Council authorization.

Paragraph 4 and 11 of Resolution 1441 lay out the process to be followed if Iraq hampers the efforts of the UNMOVIC or IAEA inspectors. Any violations are to be reported to the Security Council who will ‘convene immediately to consider the situation’³⁴. Hence, the terms of paragraph 4 Resolution 1441, make it clear that a failure of Iraq to cooperate, if reported to the Security Council, would not justify any State’s unilateral suspension of the cease-fire provision without giving the Security Council an opportunity to consider the situation and to act under paragraph 12. It is not for individual States to monitor compliance but rather for the Security Council to do so. Only the Council can decide what to do next following a violation. It will then state whether ‘serious consequences’³⁵ are called for or not.

The real problem of Resolution 1441 is the last two paragraphs which are opaque. Nevertheless, clearly there is no provision for the authorisation of the use of force in Resolution 1441. The United States and United Kingdom tried to get the phrase ‘all necessary means’ (the language recognized as authorising the use of force) into the Resolution, but other Security Council members rejected it. The replacement language, ‘serious consequences’, is not, and was not intended to be, synonymous. All the Permanent Members Ambassadors also made clear statements to the Security Council that the Resolution contained no ‘automaticity’ and ‘no hidden triggers’³⁶. An observation of this Resolution as a whole is that, it will be very difficult for any sovereign nation to comply with it because it in effect, authorizes the occupation of Iraq³⁷.

III. AN ASSESSMENT OF THE LEGALITY OF THE UNITED STATES AND UNITED KINGDOM JUSTIFICATION FOR INVADING IRAQ.

³³ UNITED NATIONS CHARTER, ARTICLE 25.

³⁴ S.C.Res 1441, *supra* note 28, at para.12.

³⁵S.C. Res 1441, *supra* note 28, at para.13.

³⁶ S.PV.4644 (8 November 2002).

³⁷ See for example, measures giving the weapons inspectors the unrestricted and unconditional right to interview Iraqi officials access to buildings (para. 5).

The first report³⁸ of Dr Blix and Dr El Baradei to the Security Council on February 14, 2003 after the adoption of Resolution 1441 welcomed co-operation by Iraq. There were some criticisms but inspections were generally going on well. The second report³⁹ given to the Council on March 7 2003 was more hopeful of the ongoing inspections being successful.

However, by March 16, 2003, it became clear that neither a Resolution authorising force nor one for the continuance of inspections will be adopted. The United States and its allies decided to give Saddam Hussein and his sons 48 hours to leave Iraq otherwise they will use force to topple them. The legality of this use of force was controversial.

Although the aim is to eradicate Iraq of its weapons of mass destruction, if the coalition does not find any weapons of mass destruction in Iraq, the legality of the war will not be affected. This is because the allies went to war asserting Security Council authorisation. Thus, the fact that weapons of mass destruction have not been found does not make the war illegal.

A. Security Council Authorisation.

The incidents of the use of force against Iraq will be briefly reviewed. Throughout the 1990s, there has been a consistency of implied authorization claims by the United States and the United Kingdom with respect to Iraq. They sought to justify the bombing of Iraqi military facilities by arguing that they were responding to breaches of Iraq's obligations under Resolution 678⁴⁰. 'If the Security Council did not act, these Nations would enforce peace and security based on declarations of threats to international peace and security rather than specific authorizations to use force'⁴¹.

Legal justification for using force in 'Operation Haven' was fuzzy. Perhaps the United Kingdom had started working its way towards humanitarian action. In 2001, the United Kingdom was more specific. It said its action is not based on Resolution 688 but to 'prevent a

³⁸ U.N.Doc. S/PV.4692 (2003), at:

<http://ods-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/N03/224/61/PDF/N0322461.pdf?OpenElement>; Cm 5769.

³⁹ <http://ods-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC>; Cm 5785.

⁴⁰ Matthew Happold, 'A talented lawyer arguing a weak case', <http://www.guardian.co.uk/Iraq/Story/0,2763,916184,00.html>

⁴¹ Susan Breau, '*Predictions of the Demise of the Collective Security System are Premature: An examination of implied Security Council authorization to use force in Iraq*', pg.29

grave humanitarian crisis'⁴². Brutos Ghali, the United Nations Secretary-General argued that authority for the United States and United Kingdom's action came from Resolution 678 and the cause of the raid was the violation by Iraq of the ceasefire Resolution⁴³. There has been no other United Nations Secretary-General former or current that has publicly supported this view.

In early 1998, after Iraq's withdrawal of cooperation with the United Nations weapons inspectors, the United States and the United Kingdom threatened to use force 'to enforce the Security Council's will'. The threat was lifted when the United Nations Secretary-General, Kofi Annan, visited Baghdad and secured an agreement permitting the return of the weapons inspectors.

The Security Council endorsed the agreement in Resolution 1154⁴⁴ (1998). The Council rejected British and United States proposals that breach by Iraq of its obligations under the Annan agreement should automatically authorise the use of force. The view that unilateral forcible responses to Iraqi violations were permitted was specifically rejected by the delegations of Brazil, China, Egypt, France, Gambia, Japan, Malaysia, Pakistan, Slovenia and Sweden.

When Iraq again withdrew cooperation in the autumn of 1998, in Resolution 1205⁴⁵ the Security Council condemned Iraqi actions as 'a flagrant violation of Resolution 687'⁴⁶ and decided, 'in accordance with its primary responsibility for the maintenance of international peace and security, to remain actively seized of the matter'⁴⁷. Again, it was indicated that there should be no 'automaticity' of response, although in conducting Operation Desert Fox in December 1998 the United States and the United Kingdom chose to ignore these views. 'But this time, consensus and willingness to be silent, which had been apparent with regards to the (earlier) actions against Iraq, were weaker'⁴⁸. China's permanent representative stated

⁴² House of Commons, *Hansard*, Debates, 26 February 2001.

⁴³ Christine Gray, 'From Unity to Polarization: International law and the Use of Force against Iraq', 13 *Eur.J.Int'l L.* 1, 9-13 (2002).

⁴⁴ S.C. Res 1154 (March, 2, 1998), U.N. Docs. S/RES/1154 (1998).

⁴⁵ S.C. Res 1205 (Nov. 5, 1998), U.N.Docs. S/RES/1205 (1998).

⁴⁶ S.C. Res 1205, *ibid*, at para.1.

⁴⁷ S.C. Res 1205, *supra*, note 45, at para.6.

⁴⁸ Gray, *supra* note 43.

that his country was ‘deeply shocked by the act and condemned it’⁴⁹. Only Japan supported the United Kingdom and United States action⁵⁰.

Thus, in reviewing the incidents of the use of force against Iraq in turn, it became evident that towards the end of the 1990’s objection was growing. ‘The build-up to the conflict illustrated the consistency of the United States and United Kingdom’s position on implied Security Council authorisation but also the crystallization of opposition to that position’⁵¹.

The British and American Governments based their legal basis for going to war with Iraq on Security Council authorisation. On March 13 2003, Whitehouse spokesman Ari Fleischer said:

The United Nations Security Council Resolution 678 authorized use of all necessary means to uphold United Nations Security Council Resolution 660, and subsequent resolutions and to restore international peace and security in the area. That was the basis for the use of force against Iraq during the Gulf War. Thereafter, United Nations Security Council Resolution 687 declared a cease-fire, but imposed several conditions, including extensive WMD related conditions. Those conditions provided the conditions essential to the restoration of peace and security in the area. A material breach of those conditions removes the basis for the cease-fire and provides legal grounds for the use of force⁵².

The United Kingdom Attorney General Lord Goldsmith on 18 March 2003 said that:

Authority to use force against Iraq exists from the combined effect of resolutions 678, 687 and 1441... Resolution 687 suspended but did not terminate the authority to use force under resolution 678. A material breach of resolution 687 revives the authority to use force under resolution 678⁵³.

The Attorney General's view appears to be that Resolution 687 which imposed a formal ceasefire after the end of the Gulf War suspended but did not terminate the authorisation to use force. A material breach of Resolution 687, combined with Resolution 1441, 'revives' the authorisation in the Gulf War Resolution 678 to use force. This line of reasoning accepts that there is no automaticity in Resolution 1441 for the use of force. This is because any violation has to be told to the Security Council first. His conclusion was that the use of force against Iraq would be legal even without a second Security Council Resolution.

⁴⁹ S/PV 3955 of 16 December 1988 at pg.5.

⁵⁰ S/PV 3955, *ibid*, at pg.11.

⁵¹ Susan Breau, *Pre-emptive Self Defence and the Axis of Evil: The Legality of the Bush Doctrine*, pg.30.

⁵² Ari Fleischer, Press Statement March 13, 2003, www.whitehouse.gov/news/briefings.

⁵³ Statement by the Attorney General, Lord Goldsmith, in answer to a Parliamentary question, Tuesday 18 March 2003.

The argument that the authorization to use force in Resolution 678 is still alive is barely plausible. An authorization for the use of force always specifies the intended objective of that force. United Nations Resolutions do not empower nations to use force for whatever reasons they wish. Resolution 678 clearly identified the invasion of Kuwait as the breach of international peace and security that triggered Security Council powers under the United Nations Charter. It does not constitute a general power for the use of force. Paragraph 2 of Resolution 678 makes clear the specificity of the authorisation: member states co-operating with the Government of Kuwait to use all necessary means to eject Iraq from Kuwait. The general view is that Security Council authorisations of force are only for limited and specific purposes.

The preamble of Resolution 678 authorizes the use of force to ensure Iraqi compliance with ‘resolution 660 (1990) and all subsequent relevant resolutions’. First, does ‘subsequent’ mean subsequent to 660 and prior to 678 that is, all Resolutions beginning with 660 in existence at the time that 678 was enacted, or does it mean all Resolutions for all time including those enacted after 678 and therefore apply to 687, 1441, and those in between?⁵⁴ It seems highly unlikely that the Security Council’s intention is to create a free-standing authorization. Thus, it would have to be the former meaning.

Second, what does ‘relevant’ mean?⁵⁵ Resolution 660 is not a disarmament Resolution. It was for the expulsion of Iraq from Kuwait. It must mean ‘relevant to Iraq’s invasion of Kuwait’ as that is all that was under consideration in Resolution 660 through 678. Resolution 678 was adopted for a specific purpose; the liberation of Kuwait and as such cannot mean having to do in any way with Iraq. It cannot be revived in completely different circumstances some twelve years later. Greenwood argues that Security Council Resolutions do not run out automatically. They remain in force until repealed. It would be argued that, in light of the emphasis in the Charter on peaceful dispute settlement, Resolution 678 could not be used as an authorization for the use of force after twelve years of cease fire, unless the Security Council says so.

⁵⁴ Robin C. Miller: <http://www.robincmiller.com>

⁵⁵ Miller, *ibid.*

Two further Resolutions relied on to support the ‘continuing authorisation’ theory are 687 and 1441. The authorisation to use force in Resolution 678 was terminated with the adoption of Resolution 687 which set out the terms of the ceasefire. Section C deals with Iraq's obligations to destroy all weapons of mass destruction but no provision of Resolution 687 links Iraq's duty to destroy all weapons of mass destruction to the authorisation to use force set out in Resolution 678. There is no language anywhere in Resolution 687 which indicates that the authorisation to use force in Resolution 678 was merely suspended by the ceasefire, pending compliance with the disarmament obligations contained in paragraphs 8-13 of that Resolution. On the contrary, paragraph 33 of Resolution 687 provided that once Iraq had notified the Security Council of its acceptance of the provisions in Resolution 687 the formal cease-fire would be effective. Iraq did notify its acceptance to the Security Council and the formal cease-fire became effective⁵⁶.

In Paragraph 6 of Resolution 687, the authorization to use force was terminated contingent only upon Iraq's compliance with Resolution 686⁵⁷. Regardless of whether Iraq is in violation of subsequent demands, the termination of force in paragraph 6 is not made conditional on Iraq's compliance with those separate conditions. It is conditional only upon compliance with Resolution 686 which required Iraq to reimburse Kuwait for its losses, release prisoners of war, remove its war material from Kuwait, and in general complete the process of ending its war with Kuwait. Resolution 686 was not a disarmament Resolution; the first such Resolution was 687.

The wording of Resolution 686, the provisional cease-fire resolution adopted before the adoption of Resolution 687 makes it clear that if the Security Council had wanted to keep the authorisation to use force alive in Resolution 687, it would have used clear language to do so⁵⁸. Paragraph 4 of Resolution 686 stated that:

'during the period required for Iraq to comply with paragraphs 2 and 3 above (the terms of the resolution), the provisions of paragraph 2 of resolution 678 (1990) remain valid'.

This indicates that the Security Council considered it necessary to explicitly state that the authorisation to use force would remain alive during the provisional cease-fire. The fact that

⁵⁶ Rabinder Singh and Charlotte Kilroy, ‘The legality of an attack on Iraq’, *Solicitors Journal*, 21 March 2003. <http://www.casi.org.uk/discuss/2003/msg01307.html>.

⁵⁷ S.C.Res 686 (March, 2, 1991), U.N.Docs. S/RES/686 (1991).

⁵⁸ Singh and Kilroy, *supra*, note.56.

the Security Council did not make the same explicit statement in Resolution 687 is the clearest indication that it did not merely intend to suspend the authorisation for the use of force⁵⁹.

The Attorney General further states that paragraph 12 of Resolution 1441:

‘does not mean that no further action can be taken without a new resolution of the council. Had that been the intention, it would have provided that the Council would decide what needed to be done to restore international peace and security, not that it would consider the matter. The choice of words was deliberate⁶⁰.’

He states that all Resolution 1441 requires is reporting to and discussion by the Security Council of Iraq's failures, but not an express further decision to authorise force⁶¹.

However this is highly doubtful. The fundamental purpose of the United Nations is to bring about peace in the world. The prohibition on the use of force is a firmly established principle. An authorization to use force must be explicit. A contrary position undermines the central purpose of the United Nations. If a party is uncertain of their legality, not only will it be at risk of acting in contravention of International Law, it will also be guilty of poor policy.⁶² From the above, it is clear the Resolutions 678, 687 and 1441 ‘golden-thread’ argument that the authorization to use force in Resolution 678 is still alive and provides a legal basis for the current United States and its allies assault in Iraq is barely plausible.

In paragraph 12 of the United States draft of Resolution 1441, on the reconvening of the Security Council upon receipt of a report of Iraqi non compliance, it said that the purpose would be ‘to restore international peace and security’. As noted above, paragraph 12 as adopted by the Council says that the purpose is ‘to secure international peace and security’. The substitution of ‘restore’ for ‘secure’ departs not only from the language proposed by the United States, but also from the language quoted above that was used Resolution 678. It could imply that the situation now is not the same as it was in 1990, when Resolution 678 was adopted⁶³.

⁵⁹ Singh and Kilroy, *supra*, note.56.

⁶⁰ Statement by the Attorney General, Lord Goldsmith, *supra*, note 53.

⁶¹ Statement by the Attorney General, Lord Goldsmith, *supra*, note 53.

⁶² Although issues of *jus in bello* will not be discussed, see for example, the current situation in present day Iraq.

⁶³ Kirgis, *supra*, note 31.

Furthermore, there was an unsuccessful effort by the United States, the United Kingdom and Spain to secure the nine votes that would be necessary in the Security Council (in the absence of a veto by a permanent member) to obtain a further Resolution that would clearly authorize the use of force. It could be argued that the effort itself shows that the proponents recognized not only that Security Council support is necessary (and that the only other permissible ground for use of force, self-defence, is inapplicable), but also that Resolution 1441 and the earlier Resolutions 678 and 687 did not clearly enough authorize the current use of force. The withdrawal of the proposed Resolution in the face of a lack of sufficient backing from other Security Council members could indicate that an essential prerequisite to the use of force is lacking. 'By consulting the United Nations, it can be argued that this ended the consistency of claims that Resolution 678 provided authority for continued (implied) unilateral action'⁶⁴.

A different approach is to see the March 2003 war as a continuation of the Gulf War. Many commentators supporting the United States and United Kingdom position believe so. They see Resolution 687 as imposing a peace treaty on Iraq which created a ceasefire situation. Iraq has breached this Resolution and therefore the war against Iraq is a resumption of hostilities. This notion relies heavily on the 1907 Hague Regulations. Article 40 of which, holds that, any serious violations of armistice will result in the recommencement of hostilities. This is a curious argument as it will only be relevant if Iraq re-invades Kuwait.

Another view is that as Resolution 678 authorized force only for the purpose of driving the Iraqi military out of Kuwait, an objective which was fully accomplished by 1991. It could be argued that, were Iraq to re-invade Kuwait, the authorisation for United Nations members to use force in Resolution 678 could be revived. A more cautious view would be that Resolution 678 is tied to a particular historical event, so a new Resolution would be needed. In the absence of an invasion of Kuwait by Iraq, Resolution 678 cannot be read as a standing authorisation for the use of force by a United Nations Member against Iraq. The bottom line is that the war needs the support of nine members of the Security Council including the five permanent members. It is clear that support is blatantly lacking.

A further matter that is usually brought up is that of regime change. Some commentators hold that even if Resolutions 678, 687 and 1441 did authorize the use of force today to disarm Iraq

⁶⁴ Breau, *supra*, note 41, at pg 32.

of its alleged weapons of mass destruction, they would not, and could not, authorize force to overthrow the government of Iraq. Resolution 1441 explicitly recognizes this by ‘reaffirming the commitment of all Member States to the sovereignty and territorial integrity of Iraq’⁶⁵.

Regime change is normally regarded as unlawful but it often accompanies action taken, as in Panama in 1989, with a variety of purportedly lawful objectives⁶⁶. In fact, Security Council Resolutions cannot authorize ‘regime change’. The United Nations Charter gives the Council no such power, and even the Council may act only within the limitations of the Charter. None of the Resolutions on Iraq authorized ‘the violent overthrow of the leadership of a sovereign nation’⁶⁷. Nevertheless, it is important to note that, realistically it is practically impossible to wage a war against Iraq without overthrowing the present government.

A major issue that was not given much weight pre-war is that of collective security. It could be argued that the war against Iraq lacks an understanding of the system of collective security. The United Nations Charters collective security premise can be seen from the opening sentences which state: ‘we the peoples of the United Nations determined...and for these ends...have resolved to combine our efforts to accomplish these aims’. This indicates the rejection of the individual use of force in International relations.

A collective security system has as its primary goal the prevention of aggression and the illegal resort to force. It is a plan for maintaining peace through an organisation of sovereign States, which pledge themselves to defend one another against attack by any aggressor long in advance of any particular conflict. It postulates an institutional framework for the use of force.

White defines collective security as ‘any collective action designed to defuse situations that endanger the peace or to combat threat to and breaches of the peace’⁶⁸. Another definition is that ‘it (collective security) purports to provide security for all states, against all states which might challenge the existing order by arbitrary unleashing of their power’⁶⁹. In a nutshell,

⁶⁵ S.C.Res 1441, *supra*, note 38, at preamble.

⁶⁶ Ian Brownlie’s lecture in memory of Lauterpatch on November, 2004. ‘The Rule of Law in International Affairs’.

⁶⁷ Ivanov of Russia, S/PV.4721 of 19 March 2003 at pg.8.

⁶⁸White , “On the Brink of Lawlessness: The State of Collective Security” in 13 *Ind. Int’l & Comp. L. Rev.*237 at p. 237.

⁶⁹ I. Claude, *Power and International Relations*, (1962), pg110.

collective security is the constitutionalisation of the use of force. An attack on one of us is an attack on all of us.

It is central to the success of collective security that States relinquish their right to employ military resources at their own will. For example, Article 2(4) of the Charter prohibits the use of force by member States and promotes the use of effective collective measures as per Article 1 of the Charter. Unilateral decisions to use force by any member of the United Nations will not suffice. Only the Security Council itself can authorize the use of force under Article 42 of the Charter. The Council cannot cede that decision to individual member States. An example of a collective action is the action against Iraq in 1991 (Operation Desert Storm).⁷⁰

Dinstein, holds that,

In exercising collective security, the Security Council is not just free to decide whether and how to use force, but it is also at liberty to determine when to do so and against whom. Since the Charter seems to give it *carte blanche* in evaluating any given situation...a privilege that the Charter withholds from any individual State or group of States acting alone.⁷¹

During the now more than a decade long dispute over Iraq's compliance with its disarmament obligations under United Nations Security Council Resolution 687 which ended the 1991 Gulf War, a majority of both the Security Council- and a majority of its permanent members- have consistently argued that it is for the Security Council as a whole, and not individual States such as the United States or Britain, to decide how to enforce its Resolutions. The United States at times seems to suggest that individual Member States have the right to use force to 'enforce' Security Council Resolutions that don't themselves authorize force⁷². It is doubtful if the administration does actually believe that⁷³.

A majority of the Security Council disagreed with the United Kingdom position and argued that no existing Security Council Resolution authorized the United Kingdom, Britain, or any other Member State to enforce Iraq's disarmament obligations imposed by Resolution 687.

⁷⁰ Another example of collective security is peace-keeping actions usually referred to as Chapter VI and a half actions. Traditional peace keeping actions such as that in Cyprus is wearing out. Peace enforcement action like that in Kosovo is now the order of the day.

⁷¹ Dinstein, *supra*, note 14.

⁷² Breau, *supra*, note 51.

⁷³ We could be sure of this in an instant if, for example, several Arab Nations decided to attack Israel to 'enforce' the dozens of Security Council Resolutions Israel has been violating for decades.

France, Russia, China and other Nations argued that only a new, explicit Security Council Resolution authorizing force against Iraq could provide a legal basis for such United States and British action. Implied authorizations will not suffice.

On the adoption of Resolution 687, the USSR and China specifically state that it was the task of the Security Council to ensure its implementation. Indeed, the final paragraph of Resolution 687 makes clear that its disarmament provisions are governed by the Security Council's resolve to decide 'such further steps as may be required for the implementation of the present resolution and to secure peace and security in the area', implying further Security Council consideration will be needed. That last statement hardly reads as a blank check to any Security Council member or any other State to act on its own to require Iraq's disarmament. Thus, once the formal cease-fire was in place the Security Council took over the task of implementing the disarmament provisions of Resolution 687. It is for the Security Council to determine how to deal with Iraq, not United Nations Member States acting unilaterally.

Moreover, the terms of Resolution 678 indicate the authorisation for the use of force is granted and monitored by the Security Council. It is inconsistent with the clear terms of Resolution 678 and indeed the whole structure of the United Nations Charter to argue one or more States could decide for themselves when and if the authorisation could be revived. The position that individual member States can respond to claimed violations of the ceasefire agreement between Iraq and the United Nations without the consent of the Security Council is inconsistent with the role of the Council and is an unsustainable view of International Law.

It could also be argued that since the Security Council has decided in Resolution 1441 that certain conduct by Iraq amounts to a material breach, but the Council did not at the same time suspend its own cease-fire and instead decided to give Iraq another chance to comply with its obligations under Resolution 687, only the Council can later decide that Iraq has not cooperated fully in the implementation of Resolution 1441 and that the cease-fire consequently is no longer in force. For example, stemming from the negotiating history of Resolution 1441 the representative of Mexico (a current member of the Security Council) said after the vote on Resolution 1441 that the use of force is only valid as a last resort and

with prior, explicit authorization from the Council. Mexico does not stand alone in taking that position⁷⁴.

The joint position of France, Germany and Russia to allow inspections to continue had the support of the majority of nations. Inspectors should have been given more time. The primary role of the Security Council in the maintenance of international peace and security must not be circumvented. France, Russia and China tried to say 'consideration' in Resolution 1441 means a further decision will be taken whilst the United States and the United Kingdom said no, it amounts to much less.

IV) CONCLUSION

A major issue that contributed to the ambiguity surrounding the legality of the war against Iraq is the way Resolutions are drafted. Lobel and Ratner argue that in drafting Security Council Resolutions three steps should be taken. First, before a Nation could use force other than in self-defence, explicit Security Council authorisation is necessary. Second, that authorisation should clearly articulate and limit the objectives for which force could be employed and third, authorisation to use force should cease with the establishment of a permanent cease-fire⁷⁵

Many prominent experts on international law have denounced the war against Iraq as being illegal. According to the International Commission of Jurists (ICJ), which is one of the most prominent international legal organisations, such 'a war waged without a clear mandate from the United Nations Security Council would constitute a flagrant violation of the prohibition of the use of force'⁷⁶. The ICJ added: 'The competency of the Security Council to authorise the use of force is not unlimited. It may only do so to maintain or restore international peace and security'. On March 20 the ICJ once again issued a statement and condemned the attack on Iraq as 'a great leap backward in the international rule of law'.

⁷⁴Kirgis, *supra*, note 31.

⁷⁵ Lobel and Ratner, 'Bypassing the Security Council: Ambiguous Authorizations to Use Force, Ceasefires and the Iraqi Inspection Regime', 93 AJIL (1999) at pg.125.

⁷⁶ www.icj.com.

Not only did traditional foes like Russia and China contest the action but the Non-aligned Movement composed of 114 States which represents 55% of the planets population and two-thirds of the United Nations membership with the three permanent members of the Security Council constituted a tidal wave of opposition against the war⁷⁷. The United Nations Secretary-General Kofi Annan also told the BBC in an interview that the United States-led invasion of Iraq was an illegal act that contravened the United Nations Charter⁷⁸. The occupant has no legitimacy and thus no more legitimacy than insurgent groups⁷⁹.

To conclude, it is the writer's firm conclusion that the war against Iraq is illegal and that the legal position taken by the United States and their allies is incorrect. Iraq was an unfortunate step back for collective security but not its demise. Afterall, the United States and the United Kingdom went to war asserting international legitimacy⁸⁰.

⁷⁷ Susan Breau, *Predictions of the Demise of the Collective Security System are Premature: An examination of implied Security Council authorization to use force in Iraq*, pg.37-38.

⁷⁸ Thursday, 16 September, 2004. BBC website: http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/world/middle_east/3661134.stm

⁷⁹ Brownlie, *supra*, at note 34.

⁸⁰ Breau, *supra*, at note.37, pg.43.